

COGNACC, a compressible coupled neutronic–thermalhydraulic simplified code for molten salt reactor fast accidental transients

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803779

ABSTRACT

This work presents the formalisation, implementation, and validation of a simplified compressible coupled neutronic–thermalhydraulic code, COGNACC, developed for the analysis of fast transients in molten salt reactors (MSR) where compressibility effects can arise. The neutronic model is formulated using a point-by-zone kinetics approach, for which the complete derivation is provided. The influence of the modeling assumptions made on the evaluation of the circulating effective delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff}^{circ}) is investigated. The physical accuracy of the implemented models and the coupling is assessed through code-to-code comparisons under transient conditions. The results demonstrate the capability of COGNACC to predict the temporal evolution of power, reactivity, and temperature with good agreement to reference calculations. COGNACC provides a simplified approach that enables extensive parametric analyses for design studies. The use of a compressible formulation further allows accounting for pressure-waves affecting neutronic kinetics feedbacks that are not represented in incompressible models. This work thus contributes to improve the understanding and modeling of coupled neutronic–thermalhydraulic behavior in MSR for fast transients.

Keywords: compressible, thermohydraulic, neutronics, point-by-zone kinetics, molten salt reactors

1. INTRODUCTION

As part of safety studies supporting the design of molten salt reactors (MSR), specific challenges arise from the liquid and circulating nature of the fuel (see Fig.1.b,c), as well as from the strong coupling between the underlying physical phenomena. In MSR, negative reactivity feedbacks are linked with the fuel temperature (Doppler effect) and the fluid density (density effect).

Fast fuel expansion causes the propagation of pressure waves, whose speeds are linked to the speed of sound. Previous studies have showed that accounting for fluid compressibility for rapid reactivity insertion leads to higher power levels [1, 2]. However, the phenomenology is not yet fully understood and most simulation codes neglect compressibility effects -treating the density as a function of solely the temperature and the density feedback as instantaneous- or require important computational resources.

In this regard, a coupled neutronics-thermohydraulic fully compressible code has been developed in order to study the phenomenology and physics of such accident and be able to carry-out numerous calculations in the design phase through its simplified approach.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the neutronic and compressible thermohydraulic models implemented in the code COGNACC. Section 3 provides the formalisation of the neutronic model along with an analysis of the hypothesis made to get a simplified expression of the effective circulating fraction of delayed neutrons. Section 4 provides a code-to-code comparison of the two coupled models.

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2. CALCULATION CODE PRESENTATION

The code developed in this work, COGNACC (FR: *Code Optimisé pour la Gestion des Accidents Compressibles et multiphasiC*, EN: Optimized Code for Compressible and Multi-phase flow Accidents), is a coupled neutronic–thermohydraulic solver employing a low order modeling approach and a multi-1D core modeling framework in Fig.1.a from the original geometry illustrated in b and c. This choice of a simplified approach is motivated by several factors: the need to enable extensive parametric studies during the design phase and the objective of reaching a greater physical understanding.

Figure 1. Reactor modeling with: COGNACC (a), neutronic Monte-Carlo code (b), neutronic Monte Carlo-thermohydraulic CFD coupled code (c). Note that the modeled reactor in (b, c) has a thermalizing reflector.

2.1. Thermohydraulic Model

For the thermohydraulic model in COGNACC, the Euler equations are solved. They correspond to mass, momentum and energy balance equations for a compressible, perfect fluid - *i.e* a fluid without viscosity nor heat conduction. The hyperbolic nature of the equations and thus the wave-like nature of the solutions allow to simulate pressure and shock waves propagation, unlike the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations [3, 4]. The 1D Euler equations are defined as :

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{pmatrix} \rho \\ \rho v \\ \rho E \end{pmatrix} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \begin{pmatrix} \rho v \\ \rho v^2 + P \\ (\rho E + P)v \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ q''' \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the fluid density, v is the velocity in the x -direction, P is the pressure, $E = e + \frac{1}{2}v^2$ is the specific total energy, with e the specific internal energy and q''' is a volumetric heat source term coming from the neutronic equations described in section 2.2.

To numerically solve the equations system, an approximate Riemann solver, the HLLC scheme [4] has been implemented. To close the system, the Noble-Able Stiffened Gas [5] equation of state (EOS) is used. This EOS is suitable for simulating liquids and is convex. The coefficients were fitted to simulate a chloride molten salt reactor with fuel composed of americium and plutonium based on data simulated using molecular dynamics. The two previous models are then coupled iteratively.

2.2. Neutronic Model : Point-By-Zone Kinetics

Compared to a solid-fuel reactor, molten salt reactors are affected by the convective transport of delayed neutron precursors. The spatial importance of a delayed neutron in the chain reaction is determined at the moment of the decay of its precursor, which may occur outside the critical region, as seen in

Fig.1.c. This out-of-core decay has an impact on the effective fraction of delayed neutrons, which must be quantified in order to adapt neutron kinetics models that were originally developed for static fuels.

Starting from the classical point-kinetics equations, a point-kinetics model with spatial zones, accounting for the distribution of precursors, was developed [6]. The aim is to model the convection of neutron precursors and to formulate an effective delayed neutron population that incorporates both spatial and spectral effects.

This results in the introduction of a spatial component for the precursors and a weighting term reflecting the relative importance of the delayed neutrons emitted.

Let $\mathbf{r} = (r, z)$ and $d\mathbf{r} = r dr dz$ in cylindrical coordinates. Let f be any function defined in a volume Ω . We define the normalization operator \hat{f} as: $\hat{f} = \frac{f}{\int_{\Omega} f d\mathbf{r}}$.

j denotes the family of delayed neutron precursors, and the subscript d stands for delayed. The modified point-kinetics equations in the COGNACC code neutronics model are given by:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dn(t)}{dt} = \frac{\rho^{stat}(t) - \beta_{eff}^{stat}}{\Lambda_{eff}} n(t) + \sum_{j=1}^J \int \omega(\mathbf{r}) \lambda_j c_j(\mathbf{r}, t) d\mathbf{r} \\ \frac{\partial c_j(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (c_j(\mathbf{r}, t) \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\beta_{j,eff}^{stat}}{\Lambda_{eff}} n(t) \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{r}) - \lambda_j c_j(\mathbf{r}, t) \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial c_j(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (c_j(\mathbf{r}, t) \mathbf{v}) = \frac{\beta_{j,eff}^{stat}}{\Lambda_{eff}} n(t) \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{r}) - \lambda_j c_j(\mathbf{r}, t) \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

In Eq.(2), $n(t)$ is the total neutron population, $\rho^{stat}(t)$ the reactivity for a static fuel, β_{eff}^{stat} the static effective delayed neutron fraction in case of static fluid, Λ_{eff} the effective generation time, λ_j the decay constant of precursor family j , $c_j(\mathbf{r}, t)$ the precursor concentration, and $\omega(\mathbf{r})$ the weighting function. In Eq.(3), \mathbf{v} denotes the fluid velocity, $\beta_{j,eff}^{stat}$ the static effective fraction of family j , and $\hat{\phi}(\mathbf{r})$ the normalized flux shape.

In this article, work has been carried out to formalise the neutronic model to account for precursors convection, in particular the weight function $\omega(\mathbf{r})$ (section 3.1), and quantify the error associated with the underlying assumptions (section 3.2).

3. FORMALISATION OF THE NEUTRONIC MODEL

3.1. Simplified Expression of the Circulating Beta

We derive here the expression of the model introduced in the previous section and in [7, 6], in order to highlight the four underlying assumptions linked to the separation of spectral and spatial effects.

We recall that the importance of a given neutron population is defined as the scalar product between the adjoint and the neutron distribution [8]. Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ denote the spatial domain, and let \mathbb{R}_+ be the set of considered energies. We introduce the operator $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle$, defined for an arbitrary function $w : \Omega \times \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and its respective adjoint function $w^\dagger : \Omega \times \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, by:

$$\langle w^\dagger \chi | w \rangle = \int_{\Omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}_+} \int_{\mathbb{R}_+} w^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, E') \chi(E') w(\mathbf{r}, E) dE dE' d\mathbf{r} \quad (4)$$

where χ is the fission emission spectrum ($\int \chi(E) dE = 1$).

Let ϕ and ϕ^\dagger denote the neutron direct and adjoint fluxes, respectively, with the adjoint flux serving as a weighting function for neutron importance. The quantity ν correspond to the average number of neutrons per fission, and Σ_f is the macroscopic fission cross section. Subscripts d and p refer to delayed and prompt neutrons. The precursor concentration and decay constant of family j are c_j and λ_j .

When delayed neutrons are born at the same location as the one of the delayed neutron precursors (DNP), the spatial distributions of the delayed neutron production rate and the DNP decay rate are identical, i.e.:

$$v_d(\mathbf{r}, E)\Sigma_f(\mathbf{r}, E)\phi(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_j \lambda_j c_j(\mathbf{r}) \quad (5)$$

For *immobile* (supercritical *stat*) fuel, the *effective* β is defined as [9, 10]:

$$\beta_{eff}^{stat} = \frac{\int \phi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, E') \chi_d(E') v_d(\mathbf{r}, E)\Sigma_f(\mathbf{r}, E)\phi(\mathbf{r}, E) dE dE' d\mathbf{r}}{\int \phi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, E') \chi(E') v(\mathbf{r}, E)\Sigma_f(\mathbf{r}, E)\phi(\mathbf{r}, E) dE dE' d\mathbf{r}} = \frac{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_d | v_d \Sigma_f \phi \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi | v \Sigma_f \phi \rangle} \quad (6)$$

Equation (5) no longer holds for circulating fuel. The effective fraction of delayed neutrons, accounting for DNP circulation, is given by [8]:

$$\beta_{eff}^{circ} = \frac{\sum_j \langle \phi^\dagger \chi_{d,j} | \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_p | v_p \Sigma_f \phi \rangle + \sum_j \langle \phi^\dagger \chi_{d,j} | \lambda_j c_j \rangle}. \quad (7)$$

Given that $\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_d | v_d \Sigma_f \phi \rangle \ll \langle \phi^\dagger \chi_p | v_p \Sigma_f \phi \rangle$ and $\sum_j \langle \phi^\dagger \chi_{d,j} | \lambda_j c_j \rangle \ll \langle \phi^\dagger \chi_p | v_p \Sigma_f \phi \rangle$ -i.e., the effective delayed neutron production rate is small compared to prompt neutrons, so the total neutron production rate remains essentially the same for both static and circulating fuel- we can approximate:

$$\beta_{eff}^{circ} \approx \frac{\sum_j \langle \phi^\dagger \chi_{d,j} | \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi | v \Sigma_f \phi \rangle} \quad (8)$$

As in [11], we highlight the static effective delayed neutron fraction by decomposing the expression into two components:

$$\beta_{eff}^{circ} \approx \frac{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_{d,j} | \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi | v \Sigma_f \phi \rangle} = \frac{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_d | v_d \Sigma_f \phi \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi | v \Sigma_f \phi \rangle} \cdot \frac{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_{d,j} | \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_d | v_d \Sigma_f \phi \rangle} = \beta_{eff}^{stat} \cdot f_{eff}^{circ} \quad (9)$$

To simplify f_{eff}^{circ} , we assume that spectral and spatial effects are separable—i.e., spectral effects are independent of the emission zone. Under this assumption, $f_{j,eff}^{circ}$ depends only on space, while spectral effects are embedded in β_{eff}^{stat} . The circulation factor $f_{j,eff}^{circ}$ is thus a function of space only and is identical for all delayed neutron populations: $\phi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}, E) \approx \phi^\dagger(\mathbf{r})$. We have:

$$f_{j,eff}^{circ} = \frac{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_d | \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_d | v_d \Sigma_f \phi \rangle} \approx \frac{\langle \phi^\dagger | \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger | v_d \Sigma_f \phi \rangle} \quad (10)$$

Note that, while the spatial distribution of delayed neutrons varies with fuel circulation, the total quantity of delayed neutrons within the fuel circuit remains unchanged: $\sum_j \int_\Omega \lambda_j c_j d\mathbf{r} = \int_\Omega v_d \Sigma_f \phi d\mathbf{r}$. Thus:

$$f_{j,eff}^{circ} = \frac{\langle \phi^\dagger | \widehat{\lambda_j c_j} \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger | \widehat{v_d \Sigma_f \phi} \rangle} \quad (11)$$

In order to minimize the number of form factors used in the system code to ensure its simplicity, one would prefer providing a single form function, assuming they are equivalent.

As the adjoint calculation is not straightforward for most calculation codes, it can be assumed that the adjoint flux has the same shape as the neutron flux for $f_{eff}^{circ} : \widehat{\phi}^\dagger \approx \widehat{\phi}$. This assumption is physically motivated by the expectation that neutron importance is greatest near the core center and should decrease towards the boundary in a manner similar to the neutron flux distribution.

Typically, if the fission rate is approximated by the flux shape, it may not hold for reactors with a moderating reflector. In practice, and because we have an homogeneous fuel, we approximate $\widehat{\nu_d \Sigma_f \phi(\mathbf{r})} \approx \widehat{\nu \Sigma_f \phi(\mathbf{r})}$ or $\widehat{\nu_d \Sigma_f \phi(\mathbf{r})} \approx \widehat{\phi(\mathbf{r})}$; and $\widehat{\phi}^\dagger \approx \widehat{\phi}$ or $\widehat{\phi}^\dagger \approx \widehat{\nu \Sigma_f \phi(\mathbf{r})}$.

The previous hypotheses yield a simplified expression for the circulating effective β based on the static effective β , where the weighting factor f_{eff}^{circ} depends solely on spatial distributions of delayed neutron precursors, fission reaction rate and/or neutron flux:

$$\beta_{eff}^{circ} \approx \beta_{eff}^{stat} \cdot \frac{\langle \widehat{\nu \Sigma_f \phi} | \widehat{\Sigma_j \lambda_j c_j} \rangle}{\langle \widehat{\nu \Sigma_f \phi} | \widehat{\nu \Sigma_f \phi} \rangle} \quad \text{or} \quad \beta_{eff}^{circ} \approx \beta_{eff}^{stat} \cdot \frac{\langle \widehat{\phi} | \widehat{\Sigma_i \lambda_i c_i} \rangle}{\langle \widehat{\phi} | \widehat{\phi} \rangle} \quad (12)$$

When the fuel is immobile, we have $\nu_d \Sigma_f \phi = \Sigma_j \lambda_j c_j$ thus $\widehat{\Sigma_j \lambda_j c_j} \approx \widehat{\nu \Sigma_f \phi(\mathbf{r})}$ and $f_{eff}^{circ} \approx 1$. Finally, emitted delayed neutrons $\Sigma_j \lambda_j c_j$ are weighted similarly to $f_{j,eff}^{circ}$ in the model:

$$\frac{dn(t)}{dt} = \frac{\rho^{stat}(t) - \beta_{eff}^{stat}}{\Lambda_{eff}} n(t) + \sum_j \frac{\int_{\Omega} \phi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}) \lambda_j c_j(\mathbf{r}, t) d\mathbf{r}}{\int_{\Omega} \phi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}) \widehat{\nu_d \Sigma_f \phi(\mathbf{r})} d\mathbf{r}} = \frac{\rho^{stat}(t) - \beta_{eff}^{stat}}{\Lambda_{eff}} n(t) + \sum_j \int_{\Omega} \omega(\mathbf{r}) \lambda_j c_j(\mathbf{r}, t) d\mathbf{r} \quad (13)$$

with:

$$\omega(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\phi^\dagger(\mathbf{r})}{\int_{\Omega} \phi^\dagger(\mathbf{r}) \widehat{\nu_d \Sigma_f \phi(\mathbf{r})} d\mathbf{r}} \quad (14)$$

To summarize, we recall the previous considered hypothesis:

- H1: the amount of delayed neutrons is small compared to prompt neutrons;
- H2: the spectral effect is independent of the emission zone for the circulating precursors weighting;
- H3: the spatial shape of the adjoint flux is identical to that of the neutron flux (or to that of the total power deposition);
- H4: the spatial shape of the spatial distribution of delayed neutron power deposition is identical to that of the total power deposition (or to that of the neutron flux).

3.2. Impact of the Choice of the Hypotheses

This section evaluates the impact of various assumptions on the simplified calculation of the circulating effective beta developed in the previous section. These assumptions were investigated on a molten salt reactor developed within the framework of the ISAC project. This reactor features a thermalizing MgO reflector as well as an elongated geometry (H/D = 2), which allows the study of specific configurations characterized by a significant increase in fission rate near the reactor boundaries and a high neutron leakage rate.

The TRANSIENT FISSION MATRIX (TFM) method [12] is used for neutronic calculations. This approach extends the classical fission matrix formalism by introducing a time-dependent component and explicitly distinguishing prompt and delayed neutrons populations, describing how neutrons born in one

region contribute to fission in another. This enables the direct evaluation of effective kinetic parameters accounting for prompt and delayed contributions.

For coupled simulations with thermalhydraulics, TFM is coupled with OPENFOAM [13, ?], an open-source CFD toolbox, used to obtain the spatial distributions of precursors $c_j(\mathbf{r})$. For neutronic simulations without fluid circulation, the TFM method is used independently to compute adjoint quantities and equilibrium neutron distributions. The corresponding results are summarized in Table I.

#	Assumption(s)	Expression of β_{eff}^{circ}	Value [pcm]	Err. [%]
1	Reference	$\frac{\sum_j \langle \phi^\dagger \chi_{d,j} \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \phi^\dagger \chi_p \nu_p \Sigma_f \phi \rangle + \sum_j \langle \phi^\dagger \chi_{d,j} \lambda_j c_j \rangle}$	56.11	-
2	H1 + H2 + H3	$\beta_{eff}^{stat} \cdot \frac{\langle \hat{\phi} \sum_j \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \hat{\phi} \nu_d \Sigma_f \phi \rangle}$ and $\beta_{eff}^{stat} \cdot \frac{\langle \nu \Sigma_f \phi \sum_j \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \nu \Sigma_f \phi \nu_d \Sigma_f \phi \rangle}$	55.23 (same value)	-1.6
3	H1 + H2 + H3 + H4 ($\hat{\phi}^\dagger \approx \hat{\phi}$ and $\nu_d \Sigma_f \phi \approx \nu \Sigma_f \phi$)	$\beta_{eff}^{stat} \cdot \frac{\langle \hat{\phi} \sum_j \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \hat{\phi} \nu \Sigma_f \phi \rangle}$	54.29	-3.3
4	H1 + H2 + H3 + H4 ($\hat{\phi}^\dagger \approx \hat{\phi}$ and $\nu_d \Sigma_f \phi \approx \hat{\phi}$)	$\beta_{eff}^{stat} \cdot \frac{\langle \hat{\phi} \sum_j \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \hat{\phi} \hat{\phi} \rangle}$	51.30	-8.6
5	H1 + H2 + H3 + H4 ($\hat{\phi}^\dagger \approx \nu \Sigma_f \phi$ and $\nu_d \Sigma_f \phi \approx \nu \Sigma_f \phi$)	$\beta_{eff}^{stat} \cdot \frac{\langle \nu \Sigma_f \phi \sum_j \lambda_j c_j \rangle}{\langle \nu \Sigma_f \phi \nu \Sigma_f \phi \rangle}$	54.75	-2.4

Table I. Impact of simplifying assumptions on the calculation of the circulating effective delayed neutron fraction. Reference values: $\beta_0 = 238.852$ pcm; $\beta_{eff}^{stat} = 148.154$ pcm.

These calculations show that the different assumptions made to compute β_{eff}^{circ} can lead to non negligible error (max -8.6%). The use of H3, according to which the shape of the adjoint is identical to that of the neutron flux or the total neutron production, induces both an error of 1.6% for the reactor under study. The larger error related to H4 (calculation #4) may arise from the thermalizing nature of the reflector, which causes a significant power deposition increase at the reactor edge, whereas the flux is less affected due to the low spatial importance of the edge region. The results thus indicate that, for the reactor considered, the deposited power provides a more suitable shape function than the neutron flux.

For non-thermalizing reflector such as steel, the deviation due to the various assumption should be of minor magnitude. This will be studied on studies on other MSR concepts. We can also note that the various assumptions lead to an underestimation of β_{eff}^{circ} , yielding a more conservative estimate.

4. COGNACC COUPLING VERIFICATION

In order to assess the fidelity of COGNACC for simulating MSR physics, the code should undergo a verification process. The thermohydraulic model implementation is currently being validated by simulating the classical test case of Sod's shock tube [14] to verify the code's ability to propagate shock and pressure waves and will be presented in future publications.

Regarding the models' coupling, a code-to-code comparison has been made using the system code LICORE developed by the CNRS specifically for molten salt reactors simulations [6]. LICORE uses a similar neutronics model and solves in a Lagrangian manner the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations. For comparison sakes, the boundary conditions are set on both code so that the inlet core temperature is

constant. In COGNACC, because this comparison case is subsonic [4], temperature and velocity are fixed at the beginning of the core domain while pressure is fixed at the end. The core is axially discretized into 100 meshes -ensuring spatial convergence- and radially homogenized into a single mesh. The total reactivity feedback is -12.2 pcm/K, and follows a sinusoidal distribution with an extrapolation length of $d = 40$ cm.

Code-to-Code Comparison on Slow Reactivity Insertions

To assess the physical behavior simulated by COGNACC, transient studies were conducted under conditions where compressibility effects are negligible, *i.e* by ensuring that the variation in pressure during the transient is almost zero for compressible calculations, so that a comparison is physically consistent. Input mass flow rate is set in LICORE so that it corresponds to the mean mass flow rate in COGNACC. Transients simulations were performed with 1s linear reactivity insertion of 50, 100 and 200 pcm, illustrated in Fig.2. With an offset below one pcm in the reactivity evolution, the results demonstrate that COGNACC accurately predicts the time evolution of core power, reactivity, and average temperature.

The differences observed in the reactivity calculation may result from the Lagrangian resolution employed in LICORE, which reduces numerical diffusion, or from differences in the treatment of the overflow, leading to variations in flow rates that directly affect $\rho - \beta$. These aspects will be further examined in future work.

Figure 2. Comparison of reactivity insertion transients for COGNACC benchmarking

5. CONCLUSIONS

COGNACC, a coupled neutronic–thermohydraulic code has been developed to enable fast transient simulations for MSR. The neutronic model has been theoretically formalised, with its underlying hypothesis clearly identified and their impact on the circulating beta quantified for a reactor with a thermalizing reflector. Future work could assess the model with a larger core and a non thermalizing reflector, such as the MSFR (Molten Salt Fast Reactor) [15]. COGNACC’s models implementation has been verified through code-to-code comparison against a reference solver, for transients calculations. Future studies will focus on simulating rapid and severe reactivity insertions, in which the limitations of existing in-

compressible codes become apparent. A multiphase flow model accounting for non-condensable gases and vaporization is also currently under implementation, as even small amounts of non-condensables can drastically reduce the speed of sound, and will be included in the forthcoming work.

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